

FORMATION OF THE WORLDVIEW OF FUTURE EDUCATION TEACHERS THROUGH THE DEVELOPMENT OF READING CULTURE

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Abstract. This article is about the content and essence of reading culture, foreign experiences on the development of reading, formation of love for books in teachers, development of reading skills, and most importantly, about shaping the worldview of teachers through reading culture.

Keywords: initiative, communication, culture of book reading, creativity, competence, individual approach, independent thinking .

Формирование мировоззрения будущих педагогов через развитие культуры чтения.

Анотация. В данной статье речь идет о содержании и сущности культуры чтения, зарубежном опыте развития чтения, формировании любви к книге у учителей, развитии навыков чтения, а главное, о формировании мировоззрения учителей через культуру чтения.

Ключевые слова: инициативность, коммуникабельность, культура чтения книг, креативность, компетентность, индивидуальный подход, самостоятельное мышление

Bo‘lajak tarbiya fani o‘qituvchilarining kitobxonlik madaniyatini rivojlantirish orqali dunyoqarashini shakllantirish

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada kitobxonlik madaniyati mazmuni va mohiyati, kitobxonlikni rivojlantirish bo‘yicha xorij tajribalari, o‘qituvchilarda kitobga bo‘lgan muhabbatni shakllantirish, mutolaa ko‘nikmalarini rivojlantirish va eng asosiysi o‘qituvchilarda kitobxonlik madaniyati orqali dunyoqarashni shakllantirish haqidadir.

Kalit so‘zlar: tashabbus, muloqot, kitob o‘qish madaniyati, ijodkorlik, kompetentsiya, individual yondashuv, mustaqil fikrlash

In the world education system, promising strategies are being implemented in order to support program activities aimed at book promotion, systematic projects aimed at

developing reading culture, and turning reading into a vital need. As part of USAID's (International quality reading project) international "Book reading project", consistent reforms have been implemented to develop the skills of students to work on the text of literary works, and to effectively apply innovative approaches to the educational process to increase the reading level. is increasing.

In the world, scientific research is being conducted to create an innovative educational environment for the development of reading culture as a factor of teachers' independent thinking, initiative and creativity. Also, special attention is paid to the scientific research on clarifying the pedagogical psychological features of the development of reading culture, coordinating the methodical system, applying advanced technologies for mastering the art of reading, and developing the competence of working with electronic educational literature.

The decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on the development strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026, in the section "Ensuring spiritual development and bringing the industry to a new level."

No. PF-4947 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 7, 2022 "On the Development Strategy for the Further Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan", April 29, 2019 "Public Opinion of the Republic of Uzbekistan" Decrees No. PF-5212 "On approval of the concept of development of the education system until 2030", dated January 12, 2017 "Development of the system of printing and distribution of book products, increase and promotion of book reading and reading culture" Decree No. PF-4789, dated September 17, 2017, "On the establishment of a commission on Comprehensive measures to develop the system of publishing and distribution of book products, increase and promote the culture of book reading and reading" Decision PQ-3271 "on the program of events" and the tasks specified in the regulatory documents related to this field are being implemented.

Formation of interest in reading is an important scientific and pedagogical problem. Its relevance is related to the constantly growing role of speech in human life, it serves as a universal means of communication, a powerful intellectual channel, in a broad sense, the spiritual formation of a person, the social activity of every person. is a necessary condition for.

Based on the above considerations, we would like to say that in recent years, the interest in learning motivations for studying is increasing. Therefore, we can see that psychologists of our republic, along with world psychologists, are not indifferent to this problem. Uzbek psychologists tried to study the problem of motivation from

different angles. However, the problem of formation of interest in reading books among students of primary school age has not been studied as a special research subject.

It is known that the literature intended for children is important in forming a positive attitude towards books. This prompted many researchers to create a history of children's literature and science. One such study was conducted by the Russian pedagogue F.I. Setina. According to the researcher, the first artistic work for children in Russia was created in the second half of the 15th century. The study of the history of statehood in Russia began at the end of the 15th century and the beginning of the 16th century. This naturally required that those who were employed in factories and factories be literate. As a result, it was necessary to find ways and methods to provide education to the working class of the population. The presence of children among the main workforce created the need to develop their literacy skills and competencies. It was concluded that one of the effective ways to meet this need is to develop the literacy and broaden the worldview of children through the creation of children's literature.

V. G. Belinskiy emphasized the great importance of books and reading in children's spiritual, cultural, artistic and aesthetic qualities, formation of reading culture, patriotic and humanistic education, preparation for work and life. In the article "About children's books", the author writes: "Education is a great work, through which the fate of a person is decided... It is books written for children that should have educational value." In order for children to read the book consistently and understand it, it is necessary to create books for them based on certain requirements. V. G. Belinskiy developed the requirements for the content of children's books and emphasized that such books should contain texts, fairy tales and stories aimed at developing children's emotions and imagination. "Books written for children should give them joy, amazement, interest, excitement, and arouse the qualities of curiosity."

In conclusion, we can say that the thinkers of the East tried to analyze the acquisition of knowledge and knowledge from the book in terms of needs. It was recognized that the creation and strengthening of these needs can be achieved mainly by taking into account the psychological characteristics of the educational process by teachers, that is, taking into account the physiological and psychological characteristics of children during the study process, and using an individual approach to them as much as possible. At the same time, the great treasure of Eastern thinkers, their advanced ideas on education and upbringing of children have not lost their

importance to this day. We used their advanced ideas as a methodological basis in our research.

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